

An Electrometric Study of Chromium Salicylate Complex Ions

J. P. Tandon and R. C. Mehrotra

The reaction of trivalent chromium with salicylate ions has been studied electrometrically. The measurements have been carried out in freshly mixed solutions as well as after ageing either at room temperature or by heating. A suitable reaction mechanism has been proposed for the titration curves obtained. The suggested mechanism has been further verified by isolating and analysing the products formed by mixing the reactants in different molar ratios. The physico-chemical study gives evidence for mono- and di-salicylate complexes whereas the disalicylate is the only product of the precipitation reactions.

Chromium belongs to the first series of transition elements and is well known to form a large number of inner co-ordination derivatives. In spite of its readiness to form co-ordination compounds, its rate of combination with organic ligands is rather slow. The slow rate of reaction has been reported by a number of workers. Even a universal chelating agent, like EDTA, forms complexes with chromium only after heating. Hence the phenomenon of ageing is very important in the study of such systems.

A survey of the literature reveals that trivalent chromium salicylate and its derivatives have been prepared by a number of workers (Calcagni, *Atti Accad. Lincei*, 1913, *ii*, 22, 157; Barbieri, *ibid.*, 1915, 24, 605; Widmer and Zickendraht, Ciba Ltd., U.S.P. 2565,898/1951; Pamfilov and Puchkova, *Zhur. Obsh. Khim.*, 1955, 26, 955). No physico-chemical study has, however, been carried out with such systems, although it has been made with dicarboxylic acids (Kuntzl *et al.*, *Das Leder*, 1954, 5, 73; cf. Shuttleworth, *J. Soc. Leather Trades' Chem.*, 1948, 32, 281; *J. Am. Leather Chem. Assoc.*, 1950, 45, 41, 799; Gustavson, *ibid.*, 1952, 47, 151; Hamm and Davis, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 3085).

A detailed study has been made on salicylic acid derivatives of beryllium (Varma and Mehrotra, this *Journal*, 1958, 35, 381), aluminium, titanium (Varma and Mehrotra, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1960, 10, 247), zirconium (Kapoor and Mehrotra, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 82, 3495), and thorium (Agrawal and Mehrotra, *private communication*). In the present investigation, such a study has been made for chromic ions.

EXPERIMENTAL

Chrome alum (violet), salicylic acid, sodium hydroxide, potassium bromate and potassium hydrogen phthalate (B.D.H., Analar), potassium permanganate (Rhodia), green crystalline chromium sulphate (T.T.), oxalic acid, manganous sulphate, and sodium thiosulphate of B.D.H. or E. Merck quality were used.

Chromium was estimated volumetrically after oxidation with potassium bromate (Kolthoff and Sandell, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1930, 2, 140). The salicylate group in the compounds was estimated by alkaline permanganate method (Bottger, "Newer Methods of Volumetric Chemical Analysis", 1938, p. 63).

Measurements of pH.—The pH measurements were carried out with a Philips pH measuring apparatus (PR 9400). The asymmetric potential of the instrument was adjusted by employing a 0.05 molar solution of potassium hydrogen phthalate. Each electrometric titration was repeated at least twice and the reproducibility was established.

All the experimental solutions for pH measurements were made in conductivity water. The molarity of all the chromic solutions refers to Cr^{3+} ions.

The pH measurements of the following systems, using violet chrome alum for the chromium solution, were carried out.

(I) 100 c.c. of $M/200$ or $M/100$ or 25 c.c. of $M/25$ chromium solution, diluted with 25 c.c. of water $\rightarrow$ immediately titrated with $M/10$ - or M -NaOH solution (Fig. 1, curves A, B, C).

(II) 25 c.c. of $M/25$ chromium solution + 1 or 3 c.c. of M sodium salicylate $\rightarrow$ immediately titrated with M -NaOH solution (Fig. 1, curves D, E).

(III) 25 c.c. of $M/25$ chromium solution + 0 to 5 c.c. of M -NaOH $\rightarrow$ raised to 50 c.c. and left overnight, after which the pH of such solutions was measured (Fig. 2, curve F).

(IV) 25 c.c. of $M/25$ chromium solution + 1 or 3 c.c. of M sodium salicylate + 0 to 5 c.c. of M -NaOH $\rightarrow$ raised to 50 c.c. and left overnight, after which the pH was measured (Fig. 2, curves G, H).

(V) 10 c.c. of $M/25$ chromium solution + 0.4, 0.8, or 1.2 c.c. of M sodium salicylate $\rightarrow$ heated on a water bath for about half an hour and then titrated with $M/25$ -NaOH solution (Fig. 3, curves I, J, K).

(VI) 25 c.c. of $M/25$ chromium solution + 1.0 c.c. of M sodium salicylate $\rightarrow$ heated on a water bath for about 4 hours and then titrated with $M/25$ -NaOH solution (Fig. 3, curve L).

A similar study was carried out with green crystalline chromium sulphate and the measurements were made of the following systems :

(VII) 100 c.c. of $M/100$ chromium solution $\rightarrow$ immediately titrated with $M/10$ -NaOH solution (Fig. 4, curve A').

(VIII) 10 c.c. of $M/25$ chromium sulphate solution + 0.8 c.c. or 2.0 c.c. of M sodium salicylate $\rightarrow$ heated on a water bath for half an hour, cooled and then titrated with $M/25$ -NaOH solution (Fig. 4, curves B', C').

(IX) 10 c.c. of $M/25$ chromium sulphate solution + 0.8 c.c. of M sodium salicylate $\rightarrow$ boiled for about 5 minutes and then titrated with $M/100$ -NaOH solution (Fig. 4, curve D').

The green crystalline chromium sulphate was a T.T. C. R. grade sample. Its analysis gave Cr, 19.6% and SO_4 , 47.01%, indicating a basic salt of the formula $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_{0.4}(\text{SO}_4)_{1.3} \cdot 4.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

DISCUSSION

System (I)

Curves A, B, and C in Fig. 1 are very much similar to the one obtained by Britton for the electrometric titration of violet chrome alum with NaOH (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2127). In curve A, the precipitation begins when about 6 c.c. of NaOH, *i.e.*, about 1.2 equiv. of alkali, has been added. In curves B and C, it starts when about 10 c.c. of NaOH, *i.e.*, about 1 equiv., has been added. The pH of the solution in all cases, when precipitation begins, is about 5.25. It is thus clear that dilution does not play any significant part and neither hastens nor delays the stage of precipitation.

These observations are in agreement with those of Britton (*loc. cit.*), who has also pointed out that even from a very dilute solution of violet chrome alum, precipitation does not begin until 1 equiv. of NaOH has been added for each atom of chromium present and when a pH of 5.3 has been attained.

FIG. 1

The above observations can be explained on the basis of the formation of a soluble basic salt with the empirical composition $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})\text{SO}_4$. That the pH of the solution at this stage is not on the alkaline side and is nearly neutral (about 5.3) indicates that instead of ionising by the simple mechanism,

$$\text{Cr}(\text{OH})\text{SO}_4 \rightleftharpoons \text{Cr}^{3+} + \text{OH}^- + \text{SO}_4^{2-},$$

the salt may have the bridge structure :

The formation of bridge structure of this type has been assumed by Bjerrum (*Ber.*, 1907, 40, 2915), Pfeiffer (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1908, 58, 317), and

Werner (*Ber.*, 1908, 41, 3447). Such structures also appear to apply to some extent to the various green varieties of chromium sulphate.

After addition of 1 mole of alkali only a very slow rise in the pH of the medium occurs although the amount of the precipitate increases gradually; a sharp rise in pH is observable only after addition of 2 moles of alkali. This appears to indicate the formation of an insoluble basic salt $[\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_2 \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}]_2\text{SO}_4$ or $[\text{CrO} \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}]_2\text{SO}_4$, the acidic nature of which might indicate a bridge structure of the type :

although the acidity may be merely due to the insoluble nature of the basic salt.

On analysis, directly after filtration, the precipitate appeared to correspond roughly with the formula suggested above, although the sulphate content decreased rapidly as the washing of the precipitate was continued.

System (II)

Except for the slightly higher curves up to 1 mole, the nature of curves D and E in Fig. 1 is the same as that of curve C. The following comparison can be drawn out :

(i). In curves D and E, at 1 mole the pH is about 5.4 whereas in curve C, it is 5.25 at 1 mole of NaOH.

(ii). Similarly, at 2 moles the pH is 5.92 and 6.08 as against 5.75 in curve C, and with 3 moles, it reaches about 10 as in the earlier cases.

The above facts clearly demonstrate that there is no immediate chelation or complex formation on mixing the reactants. The titrations were therefore repeated after allowing various mixed solutions to stand overnight.

System (III)

Throughout the entire range, the pH is lower in curve F in Fig. 2, indicating slow reaction

FIG. 2

in low ranges of pH. On ageing, $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_x(\text{SO}_4)_{1.5-x}$ appears to be hydrolysed at every step, further giving $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_{x'}(\text{SO}_4)_{1.5-x'}$ where $x' > x$. The precipitation, however, starts at a much lower pH, i.e., 3.45, when about 0.8 equiv. of NaOH has been added. Thus ageing has got a marked effect on the precipitation of basic salts and this can be easily understood, as ageing will enhance the chelation and bridge formation processes. The titration curves further confirm the existence of the second basic salt, $[\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_{2-x}\text{H}_2\text{O}]_2\text{SO}_4$.

System (IV)

Compared to curve F, the curves G and H in Fig. 2 are much lower when 0.2 to 0.5 c.c. of NaOH has been added and then become almost equal up to 1.0 c.c., and afterwards become higher. The above facts along with the identical nature of curves G and H, when the molar ratios of chromium : salicylate are 1:1 and 1:3 respectively, appear to indicate that formation of only 1:1 complex goes on according to the amount of alkali added.

The alkali added therefore is neutralised and the constant pH of the solution up to one mole of alkali can be readily explained. The gradual rise in pH after the first mole of alkali is also easily understood.

The almost identical nature of the curves G and H after addition of two moles of alkali appears to indicate that the nature of reaction is similar, i.e., $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_3^+ + \text{OH}^- \longrightarrow \text{Cr}(\text{OH})_4$.

An observation, which was repeated several times, indicated that the precipitate dissolved in excess (5 and 4 moles respectively in these cases when Cr : salicylate ratio is 1 : 1 and 1 : 3 respectively) of alkali, indicating the formations of :

according to equations (i) and (ii).

Formation of a trisalicylate derivative could have required only 3 moles of NaOH for dissolution :

Thus the experimental facts support equation (ii) showing the disalicylate formation.

System (V)

Curve I.—Two breaks are obtained when 1 or 2 moles of NaOH have been added. The reactions occurring at the various stages can be explained on the basis of the following mechanism :

The pH (2.55) at half neutralisation indicates the dissociation constant of the order of $10^{-2.55}$ (2.8×10^{-3}) for the corresponding acid :

Curve J.—The disalicylate that is formed in the beginning is dissociated as shown below :

which dissociates as :

FIG. 3

The reactions with OH^- can be explained in the following manner :

Here the half neutralisation indicates the dissociation constants of the order $10^{-2.9}$ (1.2×10^{-3}) and $10^{-6.6}$ (2.5×10^{-7}) for the corresponding acid :

Curve K.—This curve, obtained when chrome alum and sodium salicylate are taken in the molar ratio of 1 : 3, is very much similar to curve J, although slightly higher due to presence of an excess of sodium salicylate. This therefore confirms that even on boiling the disalicylate is the highest derivative formed and there is no indication of further chelation. These facts are borne out very well by analytical data presented herein.

These products were isolated after mixing the reactants in the proper molar ratios, heating for half an hour, and filtering off after keeping for an hour.

TABLE I
Analysis of the products.

No	Cr : Sal. : NaOH.	% Cr.	% Sal.	Cr : salicylate.
1.	1 : 2 : 0	13.40	72.00	1 : 2.03
2.	1 : 3 : 0	13.50	72.20	1 : 2.02
3.	1 : 5 : 0	13.40	72.54	1 : 2.05
4.	1 : 5 : 1	13.80	72.03	1 : 1.99

requires Cr, 13.74 ; salicylate, 72.03%

The data can be thus explained on the formation of disalicylate only. This is interesting in view of the observations made by Burrows and Wark (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 222) for aluminium salicylate and confirmed recently in these laboratories (*private communication*).

